

Determination of Dissociation Constant (pK) and Stability Constant of Pb^{+2} , Cd^{+2} , UO_2^{+2} Complexes of Monosodium L-Glutamic Acid

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The dissociation constant (pK) of monosodium L-glutamic acid has been determined at a constant ionic strength $\mu = 0.1M$ ($NaClO_4$) in aqueous and in different 50% (V/V) solvents, viz., methanol, ethanol, isopropanol, acetonitrile, dimethyl formamide and various concentrations of dimethyl sulfoxide by potentiometric technique, adopting Albert and Serjeant method. The pK value of $-NH_2$ group has been found to increase with increase in viscosity and ionic interactions of the solutions.

The formation, composition and stability constants of the title metal ions with monosodium L-glutamic acid have been studied polarographically, adopting DeFord and Hume's method for Cd^{+2} , Pb^{+2} ions and Lingane method for UO_2^{+2} ion. The plot of $-E_{1/2}$ VS $-\log$ ligand showed the existence of 1:1 and 1:2 complex species for Cd^{+2} , Pb^{+2} ions and 1:1 complex species of UO_2^{+2} ion in aqueous solution at 25° . The overall stabilities of the complexes formed in aqueous solution are $\log K_c = 5.74, 4.15, 3.10$ for Pb^{+2} , Cd^{+2} and UO_2^{+2} - monosodium L-glutamic acid respectively. The overall changes in free energy of the complexation reactions have also been determined.

AMINO acids containing an active $-NH_2$ and $-COOH$ group, are well known for their tendency to form complexes with metals and have great significance in biological, pharmaceutical fields and are directly involved in all the metabolic, enzymatic activities of every living being. Polarographic behaviour and metal complexes of several such amino acids or compounds have been investigated by various research workers¹⁻⁷. This communication reports the formation, composition and stability constants of lead, cadmium and uranyl complexes with monosodium L-glutamic acid. Dissociation constant (pK) of monosodium L-glutamic acid has also been determined in aqueous and in different 50% (V/V) solvents, viz., methanol, ethanol, isopropanol, acetonitrile, dimethyl formamide and in various concentrations of dimethyl sulfoxide by potentiometric technique, adopting Albert and Serjeant method.

Experimental

L-glutamic acid [$HOOC.CH_2.CH_2.CH(NH_2)COOH$] was biochem 'A grade' BDH poole, England and all other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. L-glutamic acid as such is not soluble in aqueous medium hence its monosodium salt is prepared by dissolving calculated quantity of L-glutamic acid in a standard solution of NaOH (corresponding to monosodium salt). Fresh solution of metal salts were used to avoid the effects of ageing and oxidation (if any). All solutions used in polarographic measurements had in addition to monosodium glutamic acid, metal ion, $0.1M$ $NaClO_4$ and 0.002% Triton-X-100. The entire study was carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen.

A manual polarograph with scalamp galvanometer as current recorder and S.C.E. as reference electrode have been used for recording the polarograms. The capillary used had the following characteristics in $0.1M$ $NaClO_4$ at $-0.5V$ vs S.C.E. with h_{eff} value being 48.13 cm; $m = 1.39$ mg/sec; $t = 4.3$ sec/drop in nitrogen atmosphere at 25° .

For determining the dissociation constant of monosodium L-glutamic acid, the calculated amount of monosodium L-glutamic acid corresponding to $0.01M$ per 50 ml solution in 50% solvent and $0.1M$ $NaClO_4$ (giving a total volume of 47.5 ml) is prepared. Then it was titrated against $0.1M$ NaOH in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen by adding the titrant in 10 equal portions, each a tenth of an equivalent, and pH was recorded as equilibrium reached after each addition.

All pH - measurements were made on a Cambridge benchpattern pH meter (accuracy ± 0.02 pH unit) with glass calomel electrode assembly and temperature of the cell was maintained by a thermostat (U_3 - type, German) having an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. Requisite quantities of $NaClO_4$ were added to the solution for maintaining constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1M$).

Results and Discussion

Dissociation constant:

L-glutamic acid as such is not soluble in aqueous medium, hence its monosodium salt is prepared which

exists in the form of 'Zwitterion' and may be represented as^{8,9}

The dissociation constant of monobasic acid, (I), may be determined by the following mechanism

By law of mass action:

$$K = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{NaOOC}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)-\text{COO}^-]}{[\text{NaOOC}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{}^+\text{NH}_3)-\text{COO}^-]} \quad \dots (2)$$

In dilute solutions, the concentration may be taken as equivalent to activities. Equation (2) may be written as

$$pK = pH + \log \frac{[\text{NaOOC}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{}^+\text{NH}_3)-\text{COO}^-]}{[\text{NaOOC}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)-\text{COO}^-]} \quad \dots (3)$$

Hence, for determination of pK value of monosodium L-glutamic acid, the ratio

$$\frac{[\text{NaOOC}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{}^+\text{NH}_3)-\text{COO}^-]}{[\text{NaOOC}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)-\text{COO}^-]}$$

should be known at a particular pH, and this ratio may be determined from the stoichiometric concentrations, i.e. those concentrations which would be present if each portion of the alkali reacted with its equivalent of monosodium L-glutamic acid. Expression (3) may be written as follows for the correction of hydroxyl ion concentration.

$$pK = pH + \log \frac{[\text{NaOOC}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{}^+\text{NH}_3)-\text{COO}^-] + [\text{OH}^-]}{[\text{NaOOC}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)-\text{COO}^-] - [\text{OH}^-]} \quad \dots (4)$$

The pK value of -NH₂ group of monosodium L-glutamic acid in 50% (V/V) different solvents are determined at 25°, which show the following order [Table 1].

DMSO > DMF > Acetonitrile > Isopropanol > Ethanol > Methanol

This may be partly due to change in dielectric constant¹⁰ of the medium which depends on the viscosity and ionic interactions of the solution¹¹.

The pK value in aqueous and in various concentration of DMSO has also been determined [Table 1].

TABLE 1—VALUES OF DISSOCIATION CONSTANT (pK) OF -NH₂ GROUP OF MONOSODIUM L-GLUTAMIC ACID (0.01M) AT IONIC STRENGTHS μ=0.1M (NaClO₄) IN DIFFERENT PERCENTAGES (V/V) OF NON-AQUEOUS MEDIUM AT 25°C.

Sl. No.	Medium	pK-value
1.	Aqueous (100%)	9.56
2.	Methanol (50%)	9.75
3.	Ethanol (50%)	9.77
4.	Isopropanol (50%)	9.80
5.	Acetonitrile (50%)	9.82
6.	Dimethyl formamide (50%)	10.14
7.	Dimethyl sulfoxide (50%)	10.33
8.	Dimethyl sulfoxide (40%)	10.13
9.	Dimethyl sulfoxide (30%)	9.94
10.	Dimethyl sulfoxide (20%)	9.76
11.	Dimethyl sulfoxide (10%)	9.64

Lead and Cadmium-Monosodium L-Glutamic Acid System :

Both lead and cadmium-monosodium L-glutamic acid complexes at d.m.e. give a well defined cathodic wave in aqueous medium. The reduction is found to be diffusion controlled¹², two electron reversible step for both the systems as is evident from the constant value of $i_d h_{eff}^{1/2}$ (Fig. 1) within experimental conditions and from the plots of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs $-E_{d.e.}$, whose values of slopes (0.03 ± 0.003) V, were agreeing with the theoretical value of 0.03V of two electron transfer process¹³.

Fig. 1. Plot of i_d vs $h_{eff}^{1/2}$ for

- (a) Cd²⁺ - monosodium L-glutamic acid system
- (b) Pb²⁺ - monosodium L-glutamic acid system
- (c) UO₂²⁺ - monosodium L-glutamic acid system

Effect of varying [ligand] :

The cathodic shift in $E_{1/2}$ coupled with decrease in diffusion current on increasing [ligand] 0.000M to 0.012 M [Table 2 for Cd^{+2} system and Table 3 for Pb^{+2} - system] shows the formation of complex species. The curvature obtained in the plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log$ [ligand] of both the systems showed the formation of successive complexes.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $E_{1/2}$, i_d AND VARIOUS FUNCTIONS FOR Cd^{+2} -MONOSODIUM L-GLUTAMIC ACID SYSTEM AT 25°C

Sl. No.	Concn. of ligand C_X (M)	$-E_{1/2}$ (Volts)	i_d (μA)	$F_0(X)$	$F_1(X)$	$F_2(X)$
1.	0.000	0.5890	5.47	—	—	—
2.	0.016	0.5920	5.28	1.3094	19.3375	—
3.	0.024	0.5980	5.18	2.1314	47.1417	380.90
4.	0.040	0.6030	5.03	3.2419	56.0475	—
5.	0.056	0.6062	4.88	4.2898	58.7464	370.47
6.	0.080	0.6110	4.80	6.3415	66.7688	359.61
7.	0.120	0.6177	4.75	10.8100	81.7500	364.58

TABLE 3—VALUES OF $E_{1/2}$, i_d AND VARIOUS FUNCTIONS FOR Pb^{+2} -MONOSODIUM L-GLUTAMIC ACID SYSTEM AT 25°C

Sl. No.	Concn. of ligand C_X (M)	$-E_{1/2}$ (Volts)	i_d (μA)	$F_0(X)$	$F_1(X)$	$F_2(X)$
1.	0.00	0.3950	6.05	—	—	—
2.	0.01	0.4062	5.35	2.7097	170.97	3597
3.	0.02	0.4145	5.17	5.3589	217.94	4147
4.	0.04	0.4242	4.97	11.8815	272.04	3426
5.	0.06	0.4327	4.85	23.6321	377.20	4036
6.	0.08	0.4375	4.70	35.4613	430.76	3697
7.	0.10	0.4430	4.66	54.9450	539.75	4044

Calculation of overall stability constants :

According to DeFord and Hume's method¹⁴

$$F_0(X) = \text{antilog} \left\{ 0.435 \frac{nF}{RT} [E_{1/2}]_S - (E_{1/2})_C \right\} + \log \frac{I_S}{I_C} \quad (1)$$

Herewith the sign and meaning of the terms are the same as those in¹⁵, which became conventional. The complexity function $F_j(X)$ is defined as

$$F_j(X) = 1 + \beta_1(X) + \beta_2(X)^2 + \dots + \beta_n(X)^n + \dots + \beta_N(X)^N \dots (2)$$

where (X) is the ligand concentration (C_X), n is the number of ligand molecules ; ($0 \leq n \leq N$), N is the coordination number of the complex forming, metal (M) and β_n is the overall stability constant of the complex, MX_n . From the experimental data, the complexity function $F_j(X)$ which is polynomial in (X), is set up ; the coefficient of the latter are required, β_n . Graphical extrapolation reduces the polynomial equation (2) to N-equations from which the corresponding β_n are obtained and are given below :

Composition of complex log stability values at 25°C

	Pb^{+2} - system	Cd^{+2} - system
1 : 1	2.13	1.58
1 : 2	3.61	2.57

Probably five membered ring is formed between lead and cadmium ions with monosodium L-glutamic acid¹⁶.

where M stands for Pb^{+2} and Cd^{+2} .

From the known stability constant data, values of degree of formation α_j for each complex in a system have been calculated from the following equation¹³ at 25°.

$$\alpha_j = \frac{\beta_j(X)^j}{F_0(X)} \quad \dots (3)$$

Uranyl - Monosodium L-Glutamic Acid System :

Uranyl-monosodium L-glutamic acid complex at d.m.e. gives a well defined cathodic wave in aqueous medium. Reduction is found to be diffusion controlled one electron reversible step as is evident from the constant value of $i_d/h^{1/2}t^{1/2}$ (Fig. 1), within experimental conditions and from the values of $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ which were (0.06 ± 0.006)V agreeing with the theoretical value of one electron transfer process¹⁸.

Effect of varying [ligand] :

The cathodic shift in $E_{1/2}$ coupled with decrease in diffusion current (i_d) on increasing [ligand] 0.000M to 0.016M (Fig. 1) shows the formation of complex species. The plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log$ [ligand] result in a straight line, hence the complex formed consists of only one species. The number of ligands/metal ion i.e. p. has been determined from the slope of the plots of $-E_{1/2}$ VS $-\log$ [ligand] at temperature 25° and is 0.88 ≈ 1.0.

Formation of complex species between UO_2^{+2} and monosodium L-glutamic acid may be explained as five membered ring¹⁷.

Determination of stability constant :

According to Lingane method

$$(E_{1/2})_C - (E_{1/2})_S = \frac{0.0591}{n} \log K_C - p \cdot \frac{0.0591}{n} \log C_X \dots (4)$$

Here the sign and meaning of the terms are same as those in ¹⁸ which became conventional.

From equation (4) using experimental data, stability constant is determined from the extrapolation at $-\log C_X$ or $\log [\text{ligand}] = 0$ and is found to be 3.10.

The overall changes in free energy (ΔG) of the complexation reactions follows the order :

Pb^{+2} -system $>$ Cd^{+2} -system $>$ UO_2^{+2} -system
 -1.04 K.cal/mole -0.85 K.cal/mole -0.67 K.cal/mole .

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